

Preliminary Findings on Legislative Framework relevant to P2GreenN project

EU legislation regarding waste and human excreta is complex

Human Excreta = Waste

↳ Must therefore be regulated under EU waste law.

If waste but not (≠) wastewater

↳ Permit under WFD¹ is required.

If wastewater

↳ UWWTD² applies, but not definite.

If UWWTD **does not** apply → WFD applies.

1. WFD: Waste Framework Directive
2. UWWTD: Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive.

EU legislation for fertilizers does not include excreta-derived products

Fertilising Products Regulation (CE)

↳ Every ingredient must meet the specifications of **one of 15 Component Material Categories (CMCs)**

Some CMCs include certain types of waste → types not relevant to P2GreenN activities

EU legislation regarding water reclamation is specific

Water Reuse Regulation lays the minimum requirements for water quality & monitoring

Can excreta-derived fertilizers and reclaimed water be used in organic farming?

Reclaimed water (or irrigation water) use in organic farming

↳ **Not addressed** in EU law

Regulation (EU) 2021/1165

↳ **Only listed inputs of fertilizers, soil improvers and nutrients** are authorised for use in organic farming.

Human urine or feces

↳ **Not listed** as authorised materials in products intended for organic farming.

Contact us

Deliverables

Legislations

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